

UNRAVELLING THE SEMANTICS: EXPLORING ZOONYM CONCEPTS WITHIN PROVERBIAL WISDOM

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Abstract: Proverbs, as linguistic treasures embedded in the tapestry of a culture, serve as profound conduits of collective wisdom and cultural identity. This study endeavors to delve into the semantic underpinnings of proverbs in English and Uzbek languages, with a unique focus on the zoonymic concept – the incorporation of animal names and attributes in proverbial expressions. The intricate interplay of language, culture, and symbolism within proverbs provides a rich terrain for exploration, offering insights into the shared cognitive structures of societies.

Key words: zoonyms, linguoculture, proverbs, linguocultural analysis, semantics.

INTRODUCTION

Proverbs serve as condensed capsules of cultural wisdom, reflecting societal beliefs and values. The English and Uzbek languages possess a rich reservoir of phraseological units. Expressions with a zoonym component form a distinct category, encompassing names of animals, birds, and insects. In her work "The General Theory of Proper Names," A.V. Superanskaya emphasizes that zoonyms, denoting various creatures, constitute a specialized branch within onomastics, characterized by unique traditions that vary significantly across different cultures and eras[1]. These expressions stand out for their vividness, expressiveness, and emotional impact, offering insights into the life, culture, national character, and mentality of both the English and Uzbeks. Ascribing human qualities to animals aids in portraying the strengths and weaknesses of individuals more vividly. In this investigation, we aim to unravel the nuanced relationships between zoonyms and the meanings encapsulated in proverbs, scrutinizing how these linguistic entities contribute to the cultural fabric. By undertaking a comparative analysis between English and Uzbek proverbs, we aspire to illuminate both the universality and distinctive cultural nuances in the use of zoonyms for semantic expression. As we embark on this linguistic journey, our methodology encompasses a meticulous compilation of diverse proverbs, translation processes, identification of zoonyms, and an in-depth semantic analysis. The findings of this study not only promise to deepen our understanding of the linguistic intricacies within proverbs but also offer a cross-cultural perspective on the role of zoonyms in shaping proverbial semantics. Through this exploration, we aspire to contribute to the broader

discourse on linguistic and cultural studies, fostering a nuanced comprehension of the intricate tapestry woven by proverbs in English and Uzbek languages.

METHODOLOGY

Firstly, a diverse corpus of English and Uzbek proverbs with zoonym component from various sources, including literature, folklore and contemporary language usage. The cultural and contextual factors influencing the usage of proverbs in both languages were examined and explored semantic relations between zoonyms and proverbial meanings. It was conducted a comparative analysis between English and Uzbek proverbs, examining similarities, differences and cultural variations in the use of zoonyms for semantic expression.

DISCUSSION

When it is compared phraseological units with zoonym component in two cultures, one can find both similarities and differences in the usage of animal names. Now we compare some proverbs in two languages in order to find similarities and distinguishing sides. In English, *Dog does not eat dog* means that people of the same type do not destroy one another[2]. In Uzbek, there is an equivalent for this proverb: *Qarg’a qarg’aning ko’zini cho’qimaydi*[3]. In both proverbs, meaning is the same but the situation is represented with different zoonyms and words. Another example is *‘Never fry a fish till it’s caught’*. In English culture, this proverb means man should not count on something that has not yet happened or should not make plans based on a good scenario before it has actually occurred. In Uzbek culture, there are some proverbs with similar meaning, but with other words: *‘Jo’jani kuzda sanaydilar’*, *‘Chuchvarani xom sanama’*[3]. Encouraging people not to hurry to judge is represented with the zoonym *‘fish’* in English and the words *‘chicken’* and *‘chuchvara’* (the name of Uzbek national meal) in Uzbek languages. This shows that every culture has its own beliefs and national traditions that differ from each other. Some proverbs have the same meaning and shape in different cultures. For instance, *‘First think, then speak’* - *‘Avval o’yla, keyin so’yla’*, *‘Good health is above wealth’* - *‘Sog’lik oltindan aziz’* [2-3]. These proverbs are very similar with their meaning and the words used. Furthermore, in English culture, there is an idiomatic phrase-*‘busy as a bee’* with the meaning of a person who is very busy and active or hardworking. In Uzbek culture, the concept of being hardworking is represented by using the word *‘chumoli’* (ant). The dog is the most frequently mentioned animal in English phraseological units, most likely due to its early domestication by humans. It appears in a large number of pictures: *‘dead dog’* - a worthless, useless individual, *‘dog goes back to his vomit’* - the offender is lured to the scene of the crime and so on[4]. A dog represents several facets of human life in Uzbek phraseological units. *‘A bound dog is not appropriate for hunting*, as stated in the proverb-*‘bo’ynidan bog’langan it ovga yaramas’*; *‘it suyak chaynamasa tishi chirydi’* means that *the dog’s teeth will hurt if he doesn’t chew the bone*[5]. The semantic

analysis of proverbs with the zoonym concept in English and Uzbek languages unveils intriguing patterns and cultural nuances. Through the examination of zoonyms—words or phrases that represent animals—embedded within proverbs, we gain insight into the symbolic language used by these two distinct cultures. In English proverbs, zoonyms often serve as metaphors, conveying deeper meanings rooted in cultural experiences and historical references. The comparison of these zoonyms in English proverbs with their counterparts in Uzbek proverbs provides a rich tapestry for cross-cultural exploration. It reveals the diverse ways in which animals are employed to convey wisdom, caution, or humor. Moreover, the semantic analysis sheds light on the shared values and beliefs encapsulated in proverbs across these languages. The zoonym concept serves as a cultural bridge, allowing us to trace common threads and unique expressions that resonate within each linguistic context. As we unravel the semantic layers, it becomes evident that proverbs serve not only as linguistic artifacts but also as cultural repositories that encapsulate collective wisdom.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exploration of zoonyms in proverbs offers a fascinating lens through which to understand the semantic intricacies of English and Uzbek languages. This comparative analysis not only enriches our appreciation for the linguistic diversity but also deepens our understanding of the cultural foundations embedded in these timeless expressions.

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